

2.2. SM Configuration

At the time of writing this, several important characteristics of the Star Mappers are as yet unknown to us, although we understand that they are currently studied by MATRA. Since we must nevertheless make some predictions of the attainable accuracy and magnitude limits, as well as of computing and storing requirements, we shall assume a certain configuration with the following properties.

For the telescope we assume the ARES concept with a 0.29 m diameter semi-circular pupil. The scan rate is 180 arcsec/s $\pm$ 2 % (peak error). The SM grid consists of $N = 4$ to 8 parallel and identical slits, covering a transverse field of 40 arcmin in two perpendicular segments of 20 arcmin each. The slit width, measured in the scanning (or y) direction, is $r = 1.1$ arcsec (Ref. 1, scaled to the 10 % smaller pupil). The geometrical slit configuration is further discussed below. The two photometric channels designated B_T and V_T are separated by means of a dichroic beam splitter with separation wavelength around 510 nm. With the S-20 PMT sensitivity type and the instrument transmittance given by MATRA, this should give roughly the same photon count rate in the two channels for a star of colour $B-V = 0.5$. We assume that the two detectors are synchronously sampled at 600 Hz, so that the two signals can (a posteriori) be added for improved detection capability and positional accuracy; for the photometry the two channels must of course be kept separated. The complete count records with raw photon counts are available for the scientific data analysis.

The exact number of slits is left unspecified for the time being, except for the approximate range $N = 4$ to 8. Whatever number is chosen, a non-periodic (pseudo-random) slit pattern should be used in order to minimise side-lobe problems in a survey detection mode. The preferred pattern is probably a so-called non-redundant array, in which any given slit separation ($\pm$ some tolerance depending on the width of the response function) never occurs more than once. Examples of such non-redundant arrays are the four-slit pattern with separations in proportion $/1/3/2/$ (pattern length = 6 units) and the five-slit pattern $/2/5/1/3/$ (length = 11 units). It is in fact easily shown that these particular patterns are the shortest possible ones with $N = 4$ and 5 slits, respectively.

In combination with optimized balanced numerical filters (Ref. 2), these have also the best side-lobe suppression and least sensitivity to background counts of all patterns studied with $N = 4$ and 5. For more than 5 slits, the minimum pattern lengths are not known to the author; one of the shortest for $N = 8$ slits seems to be /2/3/4/6/8/11/1/ (35 units), so that the minimum pattern length may increase roughly as $N^{2.5}$. In the filtering (folding) process, the number of samples that must be simultaneously stored and worked on is roughly given by the pattern length multiplied by 10 samples, which is about the minimum slit separation (3 arcsec) allowed by the line spread function and slit width. Thus, $N = 4$ requires an array of about 60 samples, while $N = 8$ requires some 350 samples. For a balanced filter (automatic background subtraction), 2 - 2.5 times longer arrays will be worked on (Ref. 2). The number of arithmetic operations involved in the filtering process is however only linearly proportional to N . Finally it should be mentioned that longer patterns are of course more sensitive to deviations of the scan rate from nominal: while $N = 4$ (60 samples) may just tolerate a 2 % deviation, a pattern with $N = 8$ slits (350 samples) will only tolerate 0.3 % deviation without adjustment of the filter coefficients. In view of these several disadvantages with a larger number of slits, it is of some interest to compare the cases $N = 4$ and 8 in terms of accuracy and detection limits.

With the above assumptions we derive the following count rates for the two channels as functions of the blue magnitude (B) and colour (B-V):

$$\lg(I_{BT}) = 7.53 - 0.4 B + 0.04 (B-V) \quad (1)$$

$$\lg(I_{VT}) = 7.31 - 0.4 B + 0.48 (B-V) \quad (2)$$

I_{BT} and I_{VT} are in Hz and refer to an infinitely wide slit. They are about 0.10 and 0.25 dex higher than the rates computed by MATRA, which is mainly due to our larger bandwidths (120 and 170 nm in B_T and V_T , compared with MATRA's 100 nm). When a finite slit width is considered, the rates are multiplied by the following response function depending on the star's distance (y) from the slit centre (Ref. 1):

$y =$	0	0.3	0.6	0.9	1.2	1.5	1.8	2.1	2.4"
$f(y) =$	.67	.60	.41	.22	.11	.07	.04	.02	.01

The total slit area is $2640N \text{ arcsec}^2$. Assuming the sky brightness $B = 22.5 \text{ mag/arcsec}^2$, $B-V = 0.7$ (most of the sky is in fact fainter than that), negligible stray light, and 350 Hz PMT dark count rate, we find the background fluxes:

$$I_{\text{BTO}} = 191N + 350 \text{ Hz} \quad (3)$$

$$I_{\text{VTO}} = 234N + 350 \text{ Hz} \quad (4)$$

$$I_0 = I_{\text{BTO}} + I_{\text{VTO}} = 425N + 700 \text{ Hz} \quad (5)$$

2.3. Accuracy Estimates

Using the SM configuration and dimensions of Section 2.2, we estimate below the photometric and positional precision of a single star crossing the $N = 4$ to 8 slits, and also the limiting magnitude in a survey mode. The simple (but sub-optimal) cross-correlation method is taken as basis for the detection/estimation process, which may be a more realistic approach than using the Cramér-Rao bound.

Let n_k be the sequence of photon counts produced by one of the two channels (B_T or V_T), or being the sum of both channels. We assume that n_k obey the Poisson distribution with an expected value that can be written as the sum of a constant background component (b) accounting for the sky brightness and PMT dark current, and a variable stellar component proportional to the star's brightness (a) and depending on its position (p_0) with respect to the slits:

$$E(n_k) = b + a f(ku - p_0) \quad (6)$$

Here, $f(y)$ is the SM response function, consisting of a series of superposed humps (single-slit functions), one per slit, and normalized to $\int f(y)dy = Nr$, with r being the width of each slit in the scanning (y) direction. $u = 0.3$ arcsec is the angle travelled by the star during one sample (1/600 s). The star brightness (a) is thus the count rate that would result with an infinitely wide slit. Both a and b are expressed in counts/sample.

We assume, furthermore, that the position of the star (actually its time of transit) is obtained by maximizing the cross-correlation

$$C(p) = \sum_k f(ku - p) n_k \quad (7)$$

which will of course have a maximum (for a bright enough star) at some value of p close to the true position p_0 . The background is estimated as the average of M samples sufficiently away from the slits so that $f(ku - p)$ is negligible. The star brightness is then obtained from the maximum value $C(p)$ with some appropriate scaling and correction for the background. The magnitude is finally obtained as $m = m_0 - 2.5 \lg(a)$, where m_0 is supposed to be known from the photometric calibration by standard stars.

Introducing the numbers

$$q_{ij} = \sum_k f(ku)^i f'(ku)^j \quad (8)$$

we have obtained the following expressions for the mean errors of p_0 , b , and m :

$$\sigma_p = (q_{02}b + q_{12}a)^{1/2} / (q_{02}a) \quad (9)$$

$$\sigma_b = (b/M)^{1/2} \quad (10)$$

$$\sigma_m = 1.086 [(q_{20} + q_{10}^2/M)b + q_{30}a]^{1/2} / (q_{20}a) \quad (11)$$

For the assumed configuration we have

$$q_{10} = 3.67N, \quad q_{20} = 1.64N, \quad q_{30} = 0.90N, \quad q_{02} = 2.05N, \quad q_{12} = 0.77N \quad (12)$$

From Eqn (6) we see that the uncertainty of the background level contributes little to the magnitude uncertainty if $M > q_{10}^2/q_{20} = 8.2N$. In the following we assume $M = 16.4N$, which appears realistic. Inserting numerical values from (12) we find for $N = 4$ slits:

$$\sigma_p = 0''.35 (b + 0.38a)^{1/2} / a \quad (13)$$

$$\sigma_m = 0.53 (b + 0.37a)^{1/2} / a \quad (14)$$

while for $N = 8$ slits, the mean errors are divided by $2^{1/2}$ (factors = $0''.25$ and 0.37 respectively).

For a single crossing of 4 slits of a $B-V = 0.5$ star, we find the mean errors in Table 1. For the position (p) and combined magnitude ($m = (B_T + V_T)/2$) we have used $a = (I_{BT} + I_{VT})/600$ and $b = I_0/600$, i.e. assumed that the two signals are added. In computing the mean error in $B-V$ we have taken into account that $d(B-V)/d(B_T - V_T) = 0.9$ according to Eqs (1) - (2). Table 2 gives the corresponding mean errors for a crossing of 8 slits.

Table 1. Mean errors for a single crossing of 4 slits ($B-V = 0.5$)

B	σ_p	σ_m	σ_{BT}	σ_{VT}	σ_{B-V}
8.0	.027	.040	.056	.057	.073
9.0	.046	.070	.097	.099	.13
10.0	.086	.13	.18	.19	.24
11.0	.18	.27	.37	.39	.49

Table 2. Mean errors for a single crossing of 8 slits ($B-V = 0.5$)

B	σ_p	σ_m	σ_{BT}	σ_{VT}	σ_{B-V}
8.0	.020	.030	.041	.042	.053
9.0	.035	.053	.074	.077	.097
10.0	.071	.11	.15	.15	.19
11.0	.15	.23	.32	.34	.42

The minimum detectable star brightness depends on the amplitude of the fluctuations of $C(p)$ due to background counts. With $a = 0$ (no star present), the rms fluctuation is $\sigma_C = (q_{20}b)^{\frac{1}{2}}$. Since $dE(C)/da = q_{20}$, we see that a 3-sigma fluctuation corresponds to the star brightness

$$a_{\min} = 3(b/q_{20})^{\frac{1}{2}} = 2.34 (b/N)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (15)$$

Actually, the distribution of C is not gaussian, but the 3-sigma criterion should still be useful as a rule-of-thumb.

With the background count rate of the combined channels, the resulting $a_{\min}$ correspond to $B_{\max} = 11.76$ and 11.85 for $N = 4$ and 8 , respectively ($B-V = 0.5$). This should however not be interpreted as the practical magnitude limit, since such a faint star would only have 50 % probability of detection. Defining the limiting magnitude as that of a star with 90 % detection probability for a single crossing, using the threshold $a_{\min}$, we find that

$$B_{\lim} = B_{\max} - 1.3 \sigma_m(B_{\lim}) \quad (16)$$

(again assuming normal error distribution), or $B_{\lim} = 11.3$ and 11.4 for $N = 4$ and 8 .

In conclusion it appears that a limiting magnitude of $B = 11.0$ (for $B-V = 0.5$) could be reached in a survey mode, even with only 4 slits; a larger number of slits would bring about a significant, but not dramatic, improvement of the mean errors and detection capability.

References:

1. L Lindegren: "Star Mapper Optimisation" (unpublished note, 1982 April 6)
2. L Lindegren: "Optimization of Non-Periodic Star Mapper Patterns" (unpublished note, 1982 March 3)